

Fig. S3. Serum levels of GPT and GOT from LAP-treated mice during CIA protocol. DBA1/J male mice were injected i.d. at the base of the tail with 200 μ g of CII emulsified in CFA on day 0. Mice were boosted i.d. with CII (200 μ g emulsified in IFA) on day 21. After arthritis induction, mice were treated orally with LAP (3 mg/kg and 10 mg/kg) or LEF (3 mg/kg) or saline daily. (A-B) Levels of serum ALT (A) and AST (B) in CIA mice 4 wk after boost with CII. Data points are mean \pm standard deviation. n.s., not significant.